

The Enduring Legacy of Khasi Blacksmithing: Indigenous Metallurgy and Craftsmanship in Meghalaya

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This study explores traditional blacksmithing and indigenous metallurgy among the Khasi people of Meghalaya, India, with a focus on the villages of Myllem and Nongkynrih. Drawing from oral histories, ethnographic fieldwork, and archival sources, the paper examines how ironworking practices persist as both a livelihood and a cultural expression rooted in myth, ritual, and resistance. In the modern landscape, blacksmithing in Khasi society reflects an adaptive material culture, responding to environmental, spiritual, and socio-political changes. In Myllem, smithing remains linked to ancestral knowledge, communal cooperation, and utilitarian craft, while in Nongkynrih, it embodies historical defiance especially during the Khasi resistance against British colonial intrusion. The paper also investigates the economic dynamics of local trade, seasonal production, and artisanal specialization. Despite the pressures of modernization and market competition, Khasi blacksmiths continue to forge tools essential to agricultural, domestic, and ritual life. Their work illustrates a resilience that merges technical knowledge, symbolic meaning, and cultural continuity.

Keywords: Khasi blacksmithing, Indigenous metallurgy, Cultural heritage, Ritual practices, Material culture

Introduction

Material culture, especially in the form of traditional crafts and artisanal practices, acts as a concrete reflection of the enduring legacy of ancient skills passed down through generations (Appadurai, 1986). Across cultures and epochs, humanity has been profoundly engaged in the art of making, creating objects that serve not only functional purposes but also hold deep cultural, spiritual, and aesthetic value. This tradition of craftsmanship involves the preservation and transmission of specialized knowledge, techniques, and practices, typically through mentorships, apprenticeships, and hands-on learning. Within this framework, each object crafted is a tangible connection to ancestral knowledge and cultural identity, imbuing both the artisan and the community with a sense of continuity and belonging.

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Among the Khasis of Meghalaya, indigenous technologies and artisanal practices have long played a critical role in shaping cultural, economic, and spiritual life. One of the most enduring yet under-documented traditions is that of blacksmithing and metallurgy. For the Khasi people, blacksmithing is more than just a trade; it is a living embodiment of material culture, linking the present to ancestral wisdom while adapting to the evolving socio-economic landscape. The resilience of such crafts reflects a commitment to maintaining cultural practices that extend beyond mere survival, contributing to a community's sense of self and its historical consciousness. This practice has been providing essential tools for agriculture, warfare, and domestic use. Historically concentrated in iron-rich regions such as Ri-Bhoi and parts of Eastern Khasi Hills, the blacksmithing tradition involved a unique symbiosis between clan-based knowledge transmission and local resource extraction.

The art of metallurgy among the Khasis was not merely a utilitarian craft but a respected occupation embedded within the clan and kinship networks. In recent decades, the craft has faced a decline due to industrialization, changing economic patterns, and a shift in cultural valuation of manual labour. This paper seeks to document, analyze, and interpret the traditional practices of Khasi blacksmiths, situating them within broader conversations about indigenous technology, cultural heritage, and identity.

Statement of the Problem

Despite its historical and cultural significance, traditional blacksmithing among the Khasi people is on the brink of extinction. The craft, once vital to the community's daily life and rituals, is now practiced by a small number of families, often operating in isolation without institutional support or recognition. This decline is compounded by the lack of academic documentation that systematically captures the diverse techniques, tools, clan-specific knowledge tied to this tradition. The erosion of blacksmithing's cultural importance has led to its marginalization, as mass-produced tools and modern industrial manufacturing increasingly dominate the market, leaving indigenous practices in competition with more accessible and cheaper alternatives. Moreover, economic shifts, urbanization, and changing social structures have further diminished the demand for handcrafted metalwork. As a result, the transmission of skills from generation to generation has faltered, and younger generations show less interest in carrying forward this time-honoured practice. Without immediate intervention, both in terms of academic documentation and community-driven preservation efforts, an invaluable body of indigenous knowledge and cultural heritage risks being lost forever. The potential disappearance of this craft not only threatens a specific skillset but also jeopardizes the broader understanding of Khasi identity, cosmology, and socio-cultural resilience embedded within blacksmithing practices.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

Aim

The study attempts to document, analyse, and contextualise the traditional blacksmithing and metallurgical practices among the Khasi people of Meghalaya.

Objectives

1. To trace the historical development of blacksmithing within Khasi society.
2. To document traditional techniques, tools, and processes used in ironwork.
3. To explore the social, economic, and cultural significance of blacksmithing in the Khasi cultural milieu.
4. To observe the contemporary status of the craft and challenges it faces in the modern context.

Research Methods

This study adopts empirical research, qualitative research and original findings; rooted in ethnographic practices. Data were collected through:

· Field Visits to villages known for traditional ironwork in Ri-Bhoi District and East Khasi Hills District, were conducted to observe blacksmiths at work and engage in informal conversations and observations. The fieldwork spans between 2016 to 2019 and a revisit between 2023 to 2024.

- Oral discourses and informal interviews were conducted with elder craftsmen and clan leaders to reconstruct historical practices, beliefs, and genealogies associated with blacksmithing. Blacksmiths, tool users (e.g., farmers), and community elders provided insights into the cultural valuation of ironwork. Traditional tools were photographed as part of field work.
- Books, articles, essays, journals, academic papers and online databases were consulted to understand the colonial and postcolonial perspectives on Khasi metallurgy.
- Ethical considerations were observed throughout the study, including informed consent and respect for cultural sensitivities.

Literature Review

Scholarly attention to indigenous metallurgy in Northeast India remains sparse, though foundational studies by Gurdon (1914) and Bareh (1967) mention the presence of blacksmithing among the Khasi. Recent ethnographic works (Kharmawphlang 2002; Nongkynrih 2015) have highlighted the need for cultural preservation amid modernity, but few have focused exclusively on the metallurgical tradition. Comparative studies from Southeast Asia (Childs 1994; Haaland & Shinnie 1985) suggest ritual and symbolic dimensions to ironworking that may parallel Khasi practices. This study aims to fill the lacuna by foregrounding blacksmithing as both a technical and spiritual practice in local contexts.

1. Indigenous Metallurgy and Cosmology

Globally, blacksmiths are often ascribed a dual identity, both technical and spiritual, occupying liminal roles as craftsmen, healers, and ritual specialists (Childs & Killick 1993; van der Merwe 1980). This duality is central to understanding the Khasi blacksmith's place within society.

In many African societies, blacksmiths are believed to possess esoteric knowledge, mediating between visible and invisible realms. Herbert (1993), in *Iron, Gender, and Power: Rituals of Transformation in African Societies*, examines how smiths in central

Africa wield both technical skill and symbolic authority, often linked to fertility, healing, and transformation. Similarly, Schmidt and Avery (1983) document ritual iron smelting among the Haya of Tanzania, where the furnace represents a womb and the act of forging is metaphorically linked to birthing.

These symbolic parallels are echoed in Southeast Asia. In Indonesia, traditional ironworkers called *pandai besi* are not only toolmakers but are also associated with ritual potency, often excluded from certain village ceremonies due to the perceived danger of their powers (Atkinson 1989). In the Philippines, Scott (1994) documents the precolonial importance of *panday* (smiths) among the Visayan peoples, who produced both tools and sacred weapons, maintaining clan prestige.

2. Metallurgy and Colonial Encounters

Colonial regimes often disrupted traditional metallurgical systems, introducing industrial materials and reshaping local economies. In South Asia, Dirks (1987) notes that the colonial extraction of iron and coal restructured caste-based metallurgical practices, while also diminishing ritual autonomy. In Northeast India, British military campaigns relied on imported weaponry, but paradoxically depended on indigenous craftsmen for repairs and forging, especially during campaigns in the Khasi-Jaintia hills (Gurdon 1914).

In Africa, Childs (1991) details how colonial administrations marginalized indigenous iron production in favour of European imports, relegating blacksmiths to the fringes of rural economies. However, many traditions persisted underground or were ritualized in other forms, maintaining their symbolic power even in the absence of economic viability.

The Khasi experience reflects a similar trajectory. As British rule intensified in the 19th century, especially after the annexation of the Khasi States in 1835, demand for traditional tools declined. Yet blacksmiths continued to play roles in ritual and agricultural life, particularly through the making of ceremonial knives (*waitlam*), tools for wet-rice cultivation, and weapons for local resistance such as during the U Tirot Sing rebellion.

3. Gender, Lineage, and Craft Inheritance

The inheritance of blacksmithing knowledge often follows distinct gendered and kinship patterns. In most African and Southeast Asian contexts, smithing is a patrilineal craft, passed from father to son. However, exceptions exist: in parts of Oceania, as documented by Lemonnier (1992), knowledge transmission can be matrilineal or cross-cousin based, depending on ritual taboos and social structure.

Among the Khasi, whose society is matrilineal, the inheritance of blacksmithing skills through maternal uncles (*kñi*) is especially significant. This challenges conventional assumptions about technological knowledge as inherently patrilineal and offers new insights into how craft traditions adapt within matrilineal kinship frameworks. Nongkynrih (2015) argues that such inheritance practices underscore the Khasi's broader epistemological commitment to female-centric lineage and land rights.

4. Blacksmithing and Intangible Cultural Heritage

UNESCO and global heritage bodies have increasingly recognized blacksmithing as part of intangible cultural heritage (ICH). In Japan, for instance, swordsmithing is

protected as a *Living National Treasure*, and similar efforts have been made in West Africa through community-based preservation (UNESCO 2003; Insoll 2010). However, Northeast Indian metallurgical practices have yet to be documented or protected under such frameworks, despite their historical depth.

Studies from Latin America (DeBoer 2001) and Oceania (Roth 2000) further show how craft-based identities are often key to sustaining indigenous knowledge systems. These works call attention to the urgency of documenting threatened traditions like Khasi blacksmithing before they vanish under the pressure of mechanization and cultural homogenization.

Drawing from these global studies, this research frames Khasi blacksmithing as a hybrid practice shaped by cosmology, kinship, and colonial encounters. It argues for a framework that goes beyond functionalist interpretations of metallurgy and embraces its ritual, symbolic, and mnemonic dimensions. As a craft rooted in memory and place, blacksmithing in the Khasi Hills is not merely a fading skill; it is a living archive of resistance, adaptation, and cultural vitality.

Metallurgy, Memory, and Indigenous Knowledge among the Khasis

The Khasi people of Meghalaya have developed a sophisticated tradition of metallurgy that reflects both utilitarian and symbolic dimensions of their cultural life. Khasi artisans exhibit a remarkable command of form and function, producing objects that are not only tools of daily life but also carriers of aesthetic value and cultural identity (Bendix, 1997; Sneddon, 2013). These practices have survived despite the geographical isolation of the Khasi Hills, owing largely to the strong intergenerational transmission of knowledge and the central role of craft in ritual and social structures (Hussain, 2010).

The cultural significance of blacksmithing among the Khasis is multifaceted, ranging from the production of weapons such as arrows (*u khnam*) and spears (*u sum*) used in precolonial warfare, to the creation of tools integral to agriculture and ritual life (Sneddon, 2018; Roy, 2009). Oral traditions like the dirge of ‘*U Sier Lapalang*’ and folktales such as ‘*Ka Likai*’ encode metallurgical knowledge within narratives of memory, loss, and resilience. These stories, passed down through song and spoken word, reveal the deep entanglement of metallurgy with Khasi cosmology and historical consciousness.

The connection between metalwork and spirituality is further evident in the healing practices of ‘*kynthah nar* or *thang narsaw*’, in which heated iron is ritually used to counteract afflictions attributed to ‘*u Thlen*’, a mythological serpent believed to cause misfortune. The application of metal in these contexts goes beyond its physical properties to symbolise purification and transformation, echoing the tale of *u Thlen*’s defeat through molten iron at a waterfall known as *Kshaid Daiñ Thlen* (Sneddon, 2013). These traditions are upheld by ritual specialists under the chieftainship of the *Hima Khyrim*, underscoring the link between political authority, sacred knowledge, and metallurgical practice.

In the contemporary era, Khasi forging traditions have also served as economic lifelines. Historically, iron carried by women from places like Rangjyrteh to Mawmluh, as illustrated in the tragic tale of *Ka Likai*, signifies both the economic participation of women in metalwork-related labour and the deep embedding of iron in Khasi

narratives of survival and moral caution. Such stories not only preserve mythic memory but also document the socio-economic structures that shaped Khasi life worlds. Ultimately, the metallurgical practices of the Khasi are not only techniques of transformation but also modes of cultural inscription. They reflect a worldview in which iron is not just material but medium, bridging the spiritual, the ancestral, and the everyday. This rich confluence of folklore, healing, and craftsmanship positions Khasi blacksmithing as a vital repository of indigenous knowledge deserving sustained scholarly and cultural attention.

Unveiling the ancient craftsmanship of Meghalaya's metalwork: The Firekeepers of Myllem and Nongkynrih

In the era preceding British colonial influence, the Khasi people of Meghalaya demonstrated an exceptional mastery in the extraction and production of iron, a skill rooted deeply in their indigenous knowledge and resourceful practices. This proficiency enabled them to harness iron from clay deposits rich in ferruginous content, a process that involved meticulous techniques refined over generations (Hunter, 1879). Historical accounts, such as those documented by Hunter (1879), underscore the significance of Khasi iron production. The process typically began with the identification and excavation of clay deposits known to contain high concentrations of iron. These clay beds were carefully cleared of impurities and non-iron components, a crucial step that ensured the purity and quality of the final product. Once purified, the iron-bearing clay was subjected to a smelting process conducted in small-scale clay furnaces. These furnaces, rudimentary yet effective, were designed to achieve the temperatures necessary for melting the clay and extracting the iron. The craftsmanship involved in constructing and operating these furnaces reflected the Khasi people's deep understanding of materials and their natural surroundings. The resulting iron was highly esteemed for its quality and durability. Historical figures such as Oldham, in 1863, acknowledged and praised the superiority of Khasi iron (Hunter, 1879). This reputation extended beyond local acclaim; Colonel Lister's report from 1853 noted significant exports of Khasi iron products to neighbouring regions like Assam and the Surma Valley. These exports included essential items such as hoes and pig iron, which found diverse applications ranging from agricultural tools to materials used in boat building.

The Khasi people's ability to sustain and enhance their iron production over centuries not only supported local economies but also facilitated cultural exchange and trade networks across the region. Their expertise in metallurgy exemplified a sophisticated understanding of natural resources and technological innovation within their indigenous context. The legacy of Khasi iron production stands as a testament to the ingenuity and resilience of indigenous communities in utilizing local resources to meet both local needs and regional demands. It underscores a history of technological achievement and cultural heritage that continues to resonate in Meghalaya's rich tapestry of traditions and craftsmanship.

Myllem: Crafting through Continuity

About 25 kilometers away from Shillong, the capital of Meghalaya is Myllem village,

situated in the East Khasi Hills District, along the Shillong - Cherrapunji highway. The village folks are primarily engaged in cultivation, extracting sand from the nearby stream named Umtyngngar and quarrying rocks to break them into stones. A drive along the highway is glimpses of smithies accompanied by a symphony of rhythmic notes produced by the blacksmiths working in sheds. Work at the shed commences early in the morning, with lighting the fire at 05:00 AM until breakfast time at 9 am, then resume until lunch. This routine persists until 05:00 PM.

Blacksmith's working sheds

Due to their economic constraints they rely on traditional methods and wisdom passed down by their ancestors. The residents of Myllem Village pride themselves for the practice of the age-old profession, although the almost vanishing art of blacksmithing is in a reduced scale and economically unprofitable as they have to import the iron from neighbouring state of Assam or recycle condemned iron from car workshops. As reported by Hunter in 1879, the industry is still being pursued on a much reduced scale in the Khasi Hills for producing the typical Khasi hoe called *Mohkhiew* and Khasi dao, but strictly for local markets. The Khasi hoe (*mohkhiew*) has distinctive far-projecting shoulders that set them apart from their ethnic counterparts in Northeast India. The tool features prominently in the process of soil excavation for paddy cultivation. When Peal was in Ledo and Tikak, Naga villages, east of Makum, on the south-eastern frontier of the Lakhimpur district of Assam, in 1895, he found iron implements, miniature hoes, used by the Nagas, of a similar shape to the shoulder-

Mohkhiew

Mawshut

headed celts which had been found in the Malay Peninsula and Chota Nagpur. The peculiarly shaped Khasi hoe called *Mokhiew* with its far projecting shoulders is merely an enlarged edition of the Naga hoe described by Peal and may therefore be regarded as a modern representative in iron. Given that the Khasi and Jaintia Hills are characterized by hilly terrain the people have consistently relied on manual labour. The hoe holds significant cultural value among farmers, particularly during the hill cultivation of paddy called *Krud Ksing* in Ri-Bhoi District, Meghalaya. It is a ceremonial activity where groups of farmers come together to plough the hill slopes. Its utilization in the fields by both men and women embodies a folk identity and fosters a sense of unity. Men's hoe is large and heavy in size. It is attached to the handle using an iron item called *u sop*. On the other hand, the hoe used by women folk are smaller and lighter, directly affixed to handles made of either hard wood or bamboo roots.

In villages like Myllem and Nongkynrih, Khasi blacksmiths continue to rely on traditional hand-driven bellows, preserving time-honoured methods of indigenous metallurgy. The apprenticeship often begins around the age of 15 or 16, when young boys learn the trade under the watchful guidance of experienced smiths. The training commences with mastering the critical task of lighting and maintaining a coal-fired furnace, which is aerated by manually operated bellows made from cowhide or, more recently, recycled rubber. These bellows remain a defining technical hallmark of the craft.

The forging process begins by heating iron in the furnace, followed by rigorous hammering to remove slag and prepare the metal for shaping. This is a collective effort involving three or more blacksmiths, who must work in precise coordination to avoid injury while wielding robust hammers. These hammers, comprising iron heads fixed to wooden handles are used repeatedly to shape and refine the metal through cycles of heating and pounding until the desired form is achieved. Once forged, the tool is rapidly quenched in cold water, stored in hollowed-out logs near nearby streams, which serve both practical and ritual purposes. The final stages involve meticulous sharpening and polishing using grinding stones locally known as *mawshynrut* or *mawshut*, ensuring that the blades are both functional and finely finished.

What is remarkable is the precision with which these artisans craft tools, achieving exact specifications of length, thickness, and symmetry entirely without the aid of modern measuring devices or machines. Most smithies are strategically located near water sources to facilitate the cooling process and maintain the rhythm of production.

Khasi blacksmiths are renowned for crafting a wide variety of implements, each adapted to specific tasks. These include agricultural tools such as the *mokkhiew* (hoe), forest tools like the curved *wait lyngngun* for felling trees, and household blades such as the *wait bnoh* and *wait tyngkrong*. The *wait sum*, a butcher's knife, and the *wait kynda*, a small versatile blade, are common in daily use. The *tari dab*, a kitchen knife used for slicing vegetables, fruits, and areca nuts (*kwai*), holds not only culinary utility but cultural significance; *kwai* being central to Khasi hospitality and ritual greeting practices.

Other tools include the *rashi* (weeding knife), the *sde* (axe) for logging, and mining implements like the *pixel*, historically used for coal extraction. Larger tools such as *shalyngka* (iron levers) and *shniah* (wedges) are forged from reclaimed automotive

Wait bnoh

Wait lyngun

Wait tyngkronng

steel, including vehicle axles, reflecting the adaptive reuse of materials. These tools are indispensable for lifting, breaking boulders, and quarrying stone; an essential trade in the Khasi Hills' rugged terrain. The forging of thicker *shniah* is particularly labour-intensive, demanding greater skill and strength, as they are handcrafted without mechanical assistance. Among the many distinctive iron implements crafted by Khasi blacksmiths, the *Tala Myllem*, a traditional padlock originating from the Myllem area stands out for its utilitarian value and cultural significance. Entirely handmade without the use of industrial machinery, the *Tala Myllem* exemplifies indigenous craftsmanship and mechanical ingenuity. Constructed from iron, it features an intricate internal mechanism of levers and tumblers, encased within a rectangular or cylindrical iron body. Despite its simple outward appearance, the lock's internal system is remarkably sophisticated and resistant to tampering. The making of the *Tala Myllem* demands exceptional precision. Each component like the spring, latch, keyhole, and key is hand-forged and carefully fitted to ensure smooth operation. The keys are uniquely cut to match the lock, often with long, flat shafts and distinct notches, making each *tala* and its corresponding *shabi* (key) a singular pair. This uniqueness provides a natural layer of security. Traditionally used for securing granaries, storage boxes, doors, and even village gates, the *Tala Myllem* was an important item in both household and communal contexts. While modern factory-made locks have become more widespread, the *Tala Myllem* is still respected as a symbol of traditional ingenuity. Some continue to use these locks as heirlooms or ritual items, preserving them as markers of heritage.

One of the most essential tools in the smith's repertoire is the hammer, or *tyrnem*, which comes in various sizes and head designs suited to specific tasks like carpentry, masonry, or general blacksmithing. These hammers typically feature dual heads: a broad, rounded side for driving large nails or striking heavy implements, and a narrower side for finer, more precise work. Due to repeated exposure to high temperatures, even the hammers must be intermittently cooled in water during forging sessions.

Tala Myllem

The cottage industry of blacksmithing has been a lifeline for many youths in the village, enabling them to become self-reliant, especially in the face of challenges in securing employment in spite of being graduates. The ardent effort in preserving this ancient heritage that requires dedication and hard work is a blessing to the current generation of youths like Shri B. Marbaniang a skilled vendor, dealing in *shalyngka* and *shniah*. Shri Pynbiang Khyriem works off a dilapidated workplace that reflects the harsh reality of their hand-to-mouth labour, heavily reliant on weather conditions and access to raw materials.

Amidst a line of male-owned smithies, standing proudly is Briang Kharkongor, a woman of remarkable courage and vision. Her smithy, located by the roadside, stands as a testament to her strength and determination, as she had to assume the entire responsibility of the trade after the unfortunate demise of her husband many years ago. In the Khasi society, which follows a matrilineal system, women embrace all forms of responsibility, and it is this tenacity that has enabled Briang to weather the test of time. She never walked alone on this path, as the blacksmith community rallied around her, providing unwavering support throughout the years. Grateful for the assistance she received from the men in her profession, she acknowledges their invaluable contributions. As the head of both her household and the smithy, Briang embodies resilience and determination. This endeavour has not only empowered her to educate her own children and grandchildren but has also enabled the blacksmiths to earn a livelihood and tender to the well-being of their own offspring.

Situated near the village of Myllem, Nongkynrih holds a significant place in Khasi history and oral tradition. It is regarded as the birthplace of *U Kheihñ Kongor*, the father of the legendary Khasi patriot U Tirot Sing Syiem, the sovereign leader of the Nongkhlaw State. Historical narratives trace back to November 1826, when a *Dorbar Hima* (state council) was convened in Nongkhlaw to ratify the Nongkhlaw Agreement. This treaty was formalized between U Tirot Sing Syiem and David Scott, political agent of the British East India Company. It permitted the construction of the Bridle Path connecting Ranikudam in Kamrup to Chatak in Eastern Bengal, traversing the Khasi territory through Nongkhlaw. Following the agreement, the British established a military post in Nongkhlaw. However, by April 2, 1829, following rising tensions and perceived breaches of the agreement, the Khasi Syiems, with the consent of the *Dorbar*, collectively declared war against British intrusion, thus initiating what is remembered as the Khasi People's War of Liberty. In the face of imminent conflict, David Scott is said to have escaped on horseback via an iron suspension bridge that spanned Mawphlang and Cherrapunji through Lad Mawphlang. This historic escape route is today known as the David Scott Trail. The remains of the iron bridge that still stand along this trail offer compelling evidence of indigenous metallurgy among the Khasis. Its construction points to the existence of sophisticated ironworking knowledge long before industrialization reached the Khasi Hills. This metallurgical tradition was not only technical but also deeply embedded in the sociopolitical fabric of the region.

During the Khasi resistance, iron played a pivotal role in the crafting of weapons used in guerrilla warfare. Locally forged swords, knives, bows, and arrows were manufactured in caves, forested retreats, and hidden workshops in the hills. These weapons fashioned from locally sourced iron and crafted by skilled blacksmiths became tools of both defence and assertion of sovereignty. The use of indigenous iron arms underscored the self-reliance of the Khasi warriors and their ability to mobilize traditional knowledge in their resistance against colonial encroachment.

Thus, the story of Nongkynrih and its surrounding region is not only one of historical rebellion but also a testimony to the centrality of iron-craft in Khasi political and cultural life. The continuing visibility of iron structures and the memory of locally made weapons reflect a legacy of resilience, innovation, and indigenous industry that spanned from the 18th century into the modern era.

In another part of Jalynteng Nongkynrih, a cluster of blacksmiths, while the basic practice remains the same, they employ more hand machines and specialize in crafting larger knives. In this village, the blacksmiths construct small thatched workplaces that house two or three small furnaces beneath their roofs. To fuel the fire, they use small dried branches of trees and coal. Instead of large bellows, a small handheld one is sufficient to pump air into the furnace. As the fire burns, cut pieces of metal are placed on the flames until they glow red. Then they are removed from the fire and are pounded with a hammer until the knives take shape. Then, the pieces are transported to larger workshops for processes such as filing, drilling, handle design, assembly, and sharpening. Hand bellows prove more convenient for making knives and smaller items, as opposed to the larger bellows used in the production of hoes and larger implements. A blacksmith from the area shares his experience, about his 34 who seemed unsure if blacksmithing will continue, as the authorities are not promoting their products. Being

economically disadvantaged, he is apprehensive about taking loans from banks, fearing inability to repay for knife making is not very profitable, as the prices are quite low compared to other knives sold in the market and most urban dwellers prefer steel knives. Young boys at the age of 15 years and over are trained with a hope that they will gain insight and consider pursuing this profession in the future, with a hope that blacksmithing will persist since it has been a part of their heritage for generations. The knowledge they possess today has been passed down from their forefathers. They recon it as their cultural legacy, and they strive to preserve this art.

Smti Bitil Lyngdoh and her husband Shri Tlar Sing Rynjah from Nongkynrih Jalynteng are skilled in arrow making. They have nurtured their own business and encouraged their children to establish their own enterprises in their respective cottages. Their commitment to preserving the cultural heritage of the Khasis is truly admirable and heart-wrenching to witness the humble living conditions that blacksmiths endure.

In a modest cottage at Wahtyngkai Nongkynrih, Niras Lyngdoh, son of Bitil, resides with his wife and son. Within the confines of a small hut, he engages in knife making by securely fixing the scrap iron in the machine and measuring the sizes by drawing lines. He then cuts the iron into pieces and drills holes at specific points, intended for attaching the handle later on. It is fascinating to witness the amalgamation of traditional methods with modern technology. Throughout the knife-making process, he utilizes various machines for filing, piercing, drilling, clamping, and sharpening, enabling them to work independently. The rough blades formed through hammering and filing, undergo smelting in red-hot charcoal and are then cooled by dipping them in water. The handles of the knives are made from materials like plastic (*sololoit*) or wood, which has been used since ancient times. Until the late 1960s, knives with wooden handles were primarily sold in the market. The next step involves piercing holes in the handle by

firmly clamping it in the machine. With the aid of a drill, Lyngdoh carves intricate designs on the plastic handles of the knives, captivating potential customers. It may appear easy, but without expertise, such attempts may result in loss due to damage or breakage. The subsequent process focuses on giving the knives their proper shape. Once the knives are ready, he uses a small machine to individually sharpen them, displaying both patience and a genuine love for his craft.

Mr Tlar Sing and his wife have passed on the art of making bows & arrows to their son Pochester Lyngdoh, a young archer with many awards. He takes pride in promoting the game of archery known as *rongbira* and exporting arrows and bows outside the state. He trains men and women of the village in crafting two types of arrow heads. The barbed-headed for hunting called *ki pliang* and the plain headed for archery (*rongbira*) called *sop*. The game is as old as the people themselves and the use of the red or black arrows are associated with their oral folk narrative (Diengdoh, Oral Discourses of the Khasis of Meghalaya, India, 2022). The Khasis, are fairly good archers and that their bow and arrow at one time constituted their principal weapon of offence as well as defence. The main portion of the arrow is the arrow heads or shaft that is made of iron fashioned in local smithies (Gurdon, 2012).

Besides bows and arrows, the Khasis manufacture swords usually of wrought iron and occasionally of steel. The swords are considerably long without extra handle of wood or bone. It is now mostly used by men when they perform the Khasi traditional dance. The Khasi sword used by adult male dancers is about 45 inches in length with three parts. From its base, a part of about 8 inches is a space for holding the sword. At the end of the eight inches, a portion of about 10 inches is occupied by a space towards the pointed part this portion is blunt having two iron projections on both sides. From its end to the tip it is about 27 inches, having the sharpness on its outer aspect.

The livelihood of Khasi blacksmiths, particularly those in Myllem, is intricately tied to the rhythms of the land, seasonal cycles, and the fluctuating demands of local markets. Sales of implements such as hoes (*mohkhiew*), daos (*ka wait*), and knives (*ka tari*) depend heavily on agricultural seasons, religious festivals, and orders placed by vendors from traditional markets such as *Iewduh* in Shillong. For instance, the monsoon and pre-harvest seasons see a spike in the demand for hoes and patio knives used in weeding and terrace farming, while festivals and winter months often bring requests for specialty tools, firewood-cutting daos, and implements used in meat preparation.

Despite their modest settings and limited means, these humble smithies quietly contribute to the economic and cultural wealth of the state. Their iron-craft underpins essential aspects of rural life and supports countless households engaged in agriculture, carpentry, hunting, and domestic labour. What is truly remarkable is the spirit of mutual support that binds these artisans together. The blacksmiths, many of whom live below the economic threshold, operate not in competition but in collaboration, respecting each other's specializations and lending a hand when needed. This cooperative ethos ensures that the craft, and the culture it embodies, survives through generations.

Mr. Wit Sohlang, proprietor of the only blacksmith shop in Myllem, exemplifies this spirit. He not only sells tools made by his own hand but also distributes implements crafted by other smiths in neighbouring areas. The blacksmiths here do not mass-produce identical items; rather, each focuses on a specific niche. Some excel in forging daos, others in hoes, axes, wedges, bows, arrows, or hammers. This division of labour ensures quality, reduces direct competition, and preserves the unique signature styles of each smithy.

These tools are more than mere commodities; they are essential extensions of everyday Khasi life. The *mokkhiew* is central to agricultural labour, used to break and plough the soil on hilly slopes, plains (*pynthor*), and kitchen gardens (*kper*). The *wait* is indispensable in cutting firewood, clearing forests, and building homes and bamboo bridges that span rivers and streams. Likewise, the *rashi* or patio knife aids in weeding and maintaining crop beds, while the *tari* serves multiple domestic purposes, from slicing vegetables and fruits to cutting betel nut (*kwai*), a culturally significant item in Khasi social rituals.

Together, these iron implements form the backbone of traditional Khasi subsistence and craftsmanship. In preserving this ancient knowledge, the blacksmiths are not merely forging tools, they are sustaining a living heritage rooted in self-reliance, ecological harmony, and cultural resilience.

Comparative Perspectives

The traditional blacksmithing practices among the Khasi of Meghalaya reveal striking resonances with other indigenous metalworking traditions around the world. These comparisons illuminate shared symbolic, social, and technological dimensions, while also highlighting region-specific adaptations and cosmological understandings.

In many African societies, blacksmiths are revered as ritual specialists and custodians of sacred knowledge. Among the Dogon of Mali, for instance, the blacksmith (*numu*) holds a quasi-priestly status, associated with cosmic creation and transformation (Dieterlen, 1941; Gosselain, 2000). This mirrors the Khasi view of the blacksmith not merely as a craftsman but as a mediator of ancestral power and protector of social order. Similarly, in the Dagara community of Burkina Faso, blacksmiths are believed to interact with spiritual realms and are essential to both material and ritual life (Hountondji, 1997). This sacred-profane duality is also evident in Khasi belief,

where iron tools are used in both agriculture and protective rituals (*ka shabi*).

In Southeast Asia, particularly among the Batak of Indonesia and the Hmong of Laos, blacksmithing has been closely tied to clan-based knowledge transmission and ceremonial contexts. The use of iron for both utilitarian and symbolic purposes—such as crafting weapons, musical instruments, and ritual knives—parallels the Khasi forging of tools like *ka wait* (knife), *ka sohpet* (hoe), and the *tap tyrapad* (ritual hammer). These tools are often imbued with ancestral significance and are used in rites related to fertility, harvest, and healing, comparable to practices among the Toraja and Ifugao (Eriksen, 2001; Conklin, 1980).

In the Andes, Quechua-speaking communities traditionally practiced metallurgy not just as a craft, but as an extension of sacred cosmology. As in the Khasi case, where blacksmithing is believed to have descended from divine origins (*ka jait u Blei*), Andean metallurgy was connected to deities and earth spirits, with smiths seen as ‘transformers of matter’ (Salazar, 2008). These practices were historically disrupted by colonial encounters, yet many communities have retained symbolic aspects of the craft in ritual festivals and oral history—a dynamic also observed in postcolonial Meghalaya.

A key contrast, however, lies in gender roles. While Khasi blacksmithing remains male-dominated, some African and Southeast Asian traditions allow women to participate in metallurgical processes, particularly in smelting and bellows operation (Herbert, 1993). This suggests a spectrum of gendered involvement shaped by cosmology, division of labor, and local taboos.

In terms of technique, traditional forges among the Khasis often relying on charcoal, manually operated bellows, and anvil stones, share similarities with pre-industrial technologies found in regions like rural Nepal, sub-Saharan Africa, and indigenous parts of the Philippines (Srinivasan, 2007; Friede, 1973). However, regional ecological constraints, such as forest conservation laws in Meghalaya, have led to the decline of charcoal use unlike in parts of Africa where traditional smelting has been revived as a form of cultural tourism or educational heritage (Chirikure, 2010).

Ultimately, comparative study reveals that indigenous blacksmithing across the world is not merely about shaping metal. It is about forging social bonds, mediating spiritual forces, and anchoring collective memory. The Khasi blacksmith stands in solidarity with a global lineage of artisans whose crafts are imbued with meaning, yet threatened by modernization and industrial displacement. Understanding these parallels enhances our appreciation of vernacular technologies as critical repositories of intangible cultural heritage.

Discussion

The data reveal that blacksmithing among the Khasis, particularly in Myllem and Nongkynrih is far more than a technical craft or economic occupation. It emerges as a layered cultural institution deeply embedded in memory, ritual, and identity. In Myllem, blacksmithing retains ceremonial relevance and is tied to ancestral knowledge, myth, and the everyday needs of agrarian life. Here, the smithy is not just a workplace but a generational space where embodied knowledge is transmitted through apprenticeship

and mutual labour. Tools such as the *mohkhiew* (hoe), *wait* (dao), and *tari* (knife) are not only agricultural implements but extensions of cultural continuity, symbols of Khasi self-sufficiency, and expressions of the land's demands.

In Nongkynrih, blacksmithing carries an added layer of historical consciousness. The village's association with *U Kheih Kongor*, father of *U Tirot Sing Syiem*, the famed freedom fighter, infuses the forge with a symbolic role in the narrative of Khasi resistance. The continued memory of the iron bridge from which David Scott escaped during the Khasi People's War of 1829 stands as material testimony to an indigenous metallurgical tradition that resisted colonial incursions with self-made tools and guerrilla tactics. In this context, the smithy becomes a site of defiance, endurance, and adaptation, where the clang of hammer against anvil echoes not just labour but a history of autonomy and resistance.

Across both villages, the blacksmith's forge serves as a liminal space where material, spiritual, and social forces intersect. Tools crafted are not only used in fields or kitchens but also play vital roles in rituals, ancestral appeasement, and symbolic exchanges. The *tari dab*, for example, is indispensable not only in domestic chores but in preparing offerings and ceremonial foods, while items like *shniah* and *shalyngka* wrought from the axles of vehicles represent the creative reappropriation of modern materials into traditional forms.

However, the colonial introduction of mass-produced tools and the subsequent rise of modern industrial goods disrupted the economic viability of indigenous metallurgy. Cheap imports gradually supplanted local products, diminishing both market demand and the socio-economic stature of blacksmiths. Despite this erosion, the symbolic and cultural value of ironwork persists especially in ritual contexts and oral traditions that continue to venerate the blacksmith's role in shaping both tools and community life.

Today, Khasi blacksmiths occupy an ambiguous social position. They are neither relics of the past nor fully integrated into the market-driven present. Rather, they act as cultural brokers negotiating ancestral skills and contemporary challenges, holding space for indigenous knowledge systems in a rapidly changing world. Their work continues to speak of resilience, resourcefulness, and the importance of sustaining a living tradition that connects the material to the metaphysical, the historical to the contemporary.

Conclusion

This ethnographic study of traditional blacksmithing in Myllem and Nongkynrih underscores the intricate relationship between material production, cultural identity, and historical continuity within Khasi society. Blacksmithing, far from being a mere technical skill, emerges as a vital site of ritual authority, ancestral memory, and communal resilience. The blacksmith occupies a position not only as a maker of tools but also as a cultural mediator whose craft embodies indigenous epistemologies of transformation, utility, and social cohesion (Arendt, 1958; Ingold, 2013).

Khasi metallurgy, as this study shows, is deeply embedded within the social and ritual fabric of the community. Tools forged by blacksmiths are not simply functional items, but are laden with symbolic significance in rites of passage, agricultural

cycles, and spiritual protection. The oral histories recorded from practitioners further reinforce the sacred and cosmological origins of blacksmithing, often linked to ancestral myths and divine sanction, aligning with broader anthropological observations of metalworking as a key ritualistic practice in indigenous societies (Childs, 1991; Herbert, 1993).

However, the onset of colonialism and the subsequent shifts in the postcolonial era have created pressures that have led to the marginalization of blacksmithing as a viable economic activity. The widespread availability of mass-produced, factory-made alternatives that are cheaper and more durable than their handmade counterparts has profoundly altered the landscape of metallurgy, rendering traditional forges increasingly irrelevant in the face of industrialization. As highlighted by Sillitoe (1998), indigenous knowledge systems are dynamic, and while traditional practices such as blacksmithing have been disrupted, they have also adapted in meaningful ways, blending old and new technologies to preserve their cultural relevance.

In Myllem and Nongkynrih, some blacksmiths have embraced this adaptive dynamism by integrating modern tools, such as electric grinders and welding machines, into their work. This hybrid approach allows them to retain the core cultural functions of blacksmithing, even as they adjust to the pressures of the contemporary economy. Others have diversified, producing decorative or ceremonial items tailored to the demands of the growing tourism sector, ensuring the survival of their craft within a shifting economic context. This adaptation reflects the complex negotiation between tradition and modernity, where the preservation of cultural heritage is not about resisting change but finding ways to navigate and integrate it.

Yet, despite these adaptive strategies, the future of traditional blacksmithing among the Khasi remains uncertain. The competition with mass-produced goods and the ongoing economic challenges facing rural artisans make it increasingly difficult for blacksmiths to sustain their craft in its traditional form. As modern tools and technologies continue to shape the way metalworking is perceived and practiced, the Khasi blacksmith's role as a cultural symbol is at risk of being overshadowed by the efficiencies of industrial production.

This study contributes to a broader understanding of how indigenous crafts confront the challenges of globalization and industrialization. The blacksmiths of Myllem and Nongkynrih continue to forge more than just iron—they shape collective memory, identity, and cultural resistance in a rapidly changing world. As global discourses on intangible cultural heritage gain prominence (UNESCO, 2003), it is essential to support and recognize the cultural and ritual significance of such practices, ensuring that they are not lost to the sweep of modern tools but are integrated into the evolving tapestry of Khasi cultural heritage.

Ultimately, the persistence of Khasi blacksmithing is emblematic of a broader, global challenge: balancing cultural preservation with economic survival. In order to safeguard these invaluable traditions, it is critical that indigenous crafts are supported not only through documentation and research but through ethical engagement with the communities who sustain them. The future of traditional blacksmithing among the Khasi, like many other indigenous practices, lies in its ability to adapt to modern realities while preserving its cultural integrity.

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